

Development Predictive Models and Tool for Screening Potential Endocrine-Disruptors

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Abstract

Endocrine-disruptors are a large group of anthropogenic chemicals or unintentional production chemicals that may elicit endocrine-related harmful effects on wildlife and humans. To reduce the adverse effects of endocrine-disruptors on the endocrine system of wildlife and humans, it is vital significant to identify and screen potential endocrine-disruptors from the various chemical inventories. Predictive models and tools are widely considered as an effective and powerful screening tool that can be used to efficiently and cost-effectively identify and screen potential endocrine-disruptors from various chemical inventories. In this presentation, the endocrine endpoints-related predictive models and tool developed in our group will be introduced. Especially, the endpoints will concentrate on that in thyroid system, which may include thyroid receptor (hTR), transthyretin (TTR), thyroperoxidase (TPO), sodium iodide symporter (hNIS), thyrotropin releasing hormone receptor (TRHR), thyroid stimulating hormone receptor (TSHR), and so on. In addition, a virtual screening tool referred as “ED profiler (II)” that integrated with the predictive models of aforementioned endocrine endpoints also will be reported.

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